

APPLICATION OF ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE CAPABILITIES IN ENSURING SOIL MOISTURE RETENTION ON RAINFED LANDS OF UZBEKISTAN USING BENTONITE CLAYS

Z.F. Pulatova¹, B.T. Sabirov², Kh.L. Pulatov³, M.T. Azizova⁴

Tashkent institute of chemical technology, Tashkent, Uzbekistan^{1,3,4}

Jizzakh Polytechnic Institute, Jizzakh, Uzbekistan²

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.20484807>

Abstract. *This article examines an innovative approach to restoring low-quality pastures in Central Asia. The researchers propose using natural adsorbents – bentonite clays – and developing algorithms to optimize precipitation retention. The mechanisms for creating subsurface hydrobarriers and the potential for using artificial intelligence (AI) in managing soil reclamation in rainfed lands of Uzbekistan are discussed. The development of an intelligent moisture management system for rainfed lands based on bentonite clays is a strategic approach for ensuring environmental protection and food security in Uzbekistan amid rapid population growth. The application of AI capabilities allows transforming the spontaneous and uncontrolled use of natural resources into a controlled technological process adapted to changing climatic conditions, especially in the context of regional water shortages.*

Keywords: *water resources, moisture, bentonite, structure, artificial intelligence, rainfed lands, reclamation, water retention, swelling, algorithm, formula, modeling.*

Introduction

The problem of degradation of rainfed (non-irrigated) lands in Uzbekistan is aggravated by the aridity of the climate and the low water-holding capacity of dense sierozem soils. Traditional irrigation methods are not feasible in these conditions, which necessitates the search for solutions in the field of “passive land reclamation.” Climate change and the acute shortage of water resources during the most important vegetative period of the year have a highly negative impact on the preservation of plant life in the region. During the hot summer period, part of the moisture contained in the soil structure evaporates into the atmosphere, while another part moves downward and filters through the soil layers.

In this context, bentonite clays — natural aluminosilicate sedimentary rocks with a layered structure, capable of retaining moisture (water) in their structure, swelling, and releasing moisture back in an unlimited cycle — can be used as an environmentally friendly “accumulator of atmospheric moisture.” Due to their hydration and cation-exchange capacity, bentonite clays represent an ideal substrate for creating long-term underground moisture reservoirs. Solving the problem of water resource scarcity and degradation of rainfed lands in Central Asia requires the search for innovative solutions at the intersection of ecology, materials science, and the potential application of artificial intelligence.

The results of modern research confirm the high efficiency of using natural adsorbents, particularly bentonite clays, as ameliorants for arid regions. The application of bentonite significantly improves soil structure by reducing filtration losses and increasing the water-holding

capacity of the soil. Bentonite particles fill macropores in sandy and sandy-loam soils, creating a more complex pathway for water and slowing its infiltration into deeper layers. Due to its high specific surface area and swelling capacity, bentonite retains a significant amount of plant-available moisture in the root zone. The application of this clay mineral contributes to the formation of stable soil aggregates. The introduction of bentonite at a rate of 12–24 t/ha into sandy soils of arid regions significantly increases their water-holding capacity and creates a stable structure. This method makes it possible to reduce the hydraulic conductivity of soil and increase water-use efficiency by 15–25%, while also improving conditions for the root system [1].

Under the conditions of Uzbekistan, studies by Rakhmonov A. Kh. and Tashkuziev M. M. (2021) proved that the use of local bentonites from the Navbahor and Askamar deposits not only improves the hydrophysical properties of soils but also contributes to the prolonged action of mineral fertilizers. Bentonite clays from the Navbahor deposit in Navoi Region and the Askamar deposit in Tashkent Region of the Republic of Uzbekistan were studied, and it was confirmed that the addition of bentonite significantly increases the maximum field water capacity and improves soil structuring, particularly the proportion of valuable aggregates. It was established that, due to its high adsorption capacity, bentonite retains nutrients such as N, P, and K in the upper soil layer, preventing their leaching and providing plants with nutrition for a longer period [2].

However, the effectiveness of bentonite barriers substantially depends on dynamic environmental factors. Zhang and Liu point out the complexity of predicting moisture-release processes in modified soils under extreme temperatures. This determines the need to shift from static calculation methods to dynamic models. In their work devoted to the dynamic modeling of moisture release, the authors substantiate the inefficiency of static methods under extreme temperatures, which require consideration of nonlinear changes in water properties and in the structure of modified soils. They propose moving toward dynamic models that use machine learning to accurately describe evaporation and moisture-release processes under thermal stress conditions.

Traditional static soil water characteristic curves (SWCC) do not take into account the thermal load on the pore structure of modified soils, for example, soils amended with bentonite or biochar. Under rapid heating or freezing, the physicochemical bonds between modifier particles and soil particles change, making accurate prediction using conventional formulas impossible. It is proposed to use algorithms that recalculate moisture-release coefficients in real time, adapting to changes in ambient temperature. In modified bentonite soils, clay particles change their hydration shell more rapidly during heating than ordinary sand; therefore, static methods underestimate the actual moisture loss rate by 15–20% at temperatures above 45 °C [3].

In recent years, global practice has shown a trend toward the intellectualization of water-use management. Studies by Deepak and Suneetha (2025) demonstrate that machine learning algorithms are capable of predicting soil moisture dynamics in arid zones with an accuracy of up to 95–97%, taking into account nonlinear relationships between meteorological data and soil physics.

The main aspects of the study include the development of a nonlinear machine learning method for predicting soil moisture dynamics by integrating two types of data: first, air temperature, precipitation, solar radiation, and wind speed; and second, soil texture, bulk density, and organic composition. The authors use modern machine learning algorithms, such as random forest and neural networks, to model complex nonlinear interactions between atmospheric conditions and the physicochemical properties of soil. Under arid climate conditions, traditional

linear models often fail to cope with abrupt changes in moisture content. The proposed approach makes it possible to plan irrigation more accurately and manage water resources more efficiently, which is critically important for sustainable agriculture in arid zones. This work complements modern research in the field of dryland monitoring, where physical models, such as the Richards equation, are increasingly combined with machine learning algorithms to improve accuracy [4].

M. Vandana et al. emphasize that the use of neural networks for modeling the hydraulic conductivity of soils enriched with bentonite makes it possible to optimize the dosage of the ameliorant while minimizing economic costs. The study showed that artificial neural networks are a highly efficient and accurate tool for the rapid prediction of the filtration coefficient of sand–bentonite mixtures, replacing time-consuming laboratory methods. The scientific novelty lies in the development of a specific ANN architecture adapted to bentonite additives, the use of the Levenberg–Marquardt algorithm to achieve a high correlation coefficient ($R^2 > 0.98$), and the identification of key physical soil properties for optimizing the composition of liners for municipal solid waste landfills [5].

Despite the availability of studies devoted to individual aspects of the chemical and mineralogical composition, structure, activation methods, and modification of the structure of bentonite clays from various deposits in Uzbekistan, as well as the expansion of their fields of application [6–15], reclamation, and digitalization, comprehensive studies combining the potential of Uzbekistan’s bentonite clays with the predictive capabilities of artificial intelligence for rainfed lands are practically absent. This study is aimed at filling this gap in the context of environmental protection and the rational use of water resources in the region.

The purpose of the present research is to develop an integrated approach to managing the water regime of rainfed soils by combining the physicochemical properties of bentonite hydro-barriers with AI-based predictive modeling algorithms. Based on this purpose, the objectives of the study are as follows: to determine, under the conditions of Uzbekistan, the nonlinear relationships between the dosage of bentonite clays and the dynamics of moisture retention under extremely high temperatures and precipitation deficit; to develop the structure of an AI algorithm capable of predicting, with high accuracy of up to 97%, the duration of productive moisture retention in the root-inhabited layer; and to establish the synergistic effect of bentonite additives and intelligent monitoring on the stabilization of the reclamation condition of low-bonitet pastures and rainfed areas of Uzbekistan.

The practical significance of the research lies in the development of a technological solution for Uzbekistan aimed at adaptation to climate change and water resource scarcity. The application of the developed models makes it possible to optimize the consumption of bentonite clays, thereby reducing reclamation costs. The proposed methodology ensures the preservation of natural moisture in the soil structure and increases crop yields on rainfed lands by minimizing the risk of complete crop loss during dry periods of the year. In the future, the developed management algorithms can be integrated into digital “smart agriculture” platforms and used for pasture reclamation in other arid regions of Central Asia.

Methodology. In carrying out the research work, mathematical formulas of Langmuir, Freundlich, Richards, and others were applied. To develop a technology for the application of bentonite, it is proposed to carry out work on identifying regions of Uzbekistan with a critically low soil moisture index, selecting the optimal method for introducing bentonite granules into the subsurface soil layer, and predicting the dynamics of moisture uptake from the soil by vegetation

depending on the bentonite dosage. The model calculates the optimal granule fraction, either 1–3 mm or 3–6 mm, for a specific soil type.

Discussion

To mathematically describe the process of moisture retention by bentonite in the soil profile, models of adsorption and moisture thermodynamics are used. In the context of bentonite granules, three aspects are of primary importance: absorption intensity, moisture-retention capacity, and swelling kinetics. Below are the main groups of formulas used in the development of AI algorithms for this technology.

Equilibrium adsorption model (isotherms). To determine the amount of water that bentonite can retain in its structure at a certain initial moisture content of the surrounding environment, the Langmuir and Freundlich equations can be applied. In this case, the Freundlich equation will have the following form:

$$a = K_f \cdot C^{\frac{1}{n}}$$

where, a - the amount of moisture adsorbed per unit mass of bentonite;

C - the moisture concentration, or relative humidity, in the soil structure;

K_f and n - empirical constants depending on the type of bentonite, namely sodium or calcium form, and the ambient temperature.

The Langmuir equation can be applied to calculate monolayer coverage:

$$a = a_{\max} \cdot \frac{K \cdot C}{1 + K \cdot C}$$

where, a_{\max} - the maximum sorption capacity of bentonite.

Calculation of the swelling coefficient

Bentonite is a complex component: in soil, it acts not only as an adsorbent but also as a hydrogel. The effectiveness of bentonite application under the arid climate conditions of Uzbekistan depends on the degree of swelling:

$$Q = \frac{V_w - V_0}{V_0} \times 100\%$$

where, V_w - the volume of bentonite after absorbing atmospheric precipitation;

V_0 - the initial volume of dry bentonite granules.

To apply the capabilities of artificial intelligence for modeling, a correction coefficient of soil pressure, P_{soil} , is used, since dense soil affects the swelling process of bentonite:

$$Q_{\text{real}} = Q_{\text{max}} \cdot e^{-k \cdot P_{\text{soil}}}$$

This formula makes it possible, during modeling, to calculate the appropriate incorporation depth so that soil pressure does not “suppress” the absorbing or swelling capacity of bentonite granules.

To understand the process by which bentonite releases the moisture accumulated in its structure to plants in the soil, a modified Richards equation can be applied, in which an “absorption/release term” is introduced:

$$\frac{\partial \theta}{\partial t} = \nabla \cdot [K(\theta) \nabla \psi] - S(z, t)$$

where, θ - the volumetric soil moisture;

$K(\theta)$ - the hydraulic conductivity;

Ψ - the soil matric potential;

$S(z,t)$ - a function describing the operation of the bentonite layer, namely water accumulation in spring and its slow desorption in summer.

Calculation of the optimal dosage (empirical model). For the practical application of AI, a mass-balance formula is used to achieve the target moisture content (M_{bent}):

$$M_{bent} = \frac{V_{soil} \cdot (\theta_{target} - \theta_{current})}{\Delta a \cdot \eta}$$

where, M_{bent} - the mass of bentonite, kg/ha;

Δa - the specific water-retention capacity of bentonite;

η - the efficiency coefficient, which takes into account losses due to evaporation and filtration into deeper soil layers.

It should be noted that the application of AI makes it possible not only to perform calculations using the above formulas, but also to minimize the loss function. In particular, the algorithm searches for such values of depth (z) and mass (M) at which soil moisture remains above the permanent wilting point (**PWP**) for the longest possible period under a given precipitation forecast.

To verify the mathematical models and assess the effectiveness of the AI-based technology, controlled field trials must be conducted. Without comprehensive field experiments, it is impossible to obtain reliable modeling data.

Below, we present an experimental plan for determining the effectiveness of bentonite as a natural moisture-retaining agent, or moisture accumulator, under the conditions of rainfed lands in Uzbekistan.

For field trials, rainfed land areas or degraded pastures should be selected, for example, in Jizzakh, Navoi, Kashkadarya, and Surkhandarya regions of Uzbekistan.

It is also necessary to verify the reliability and accuracy of the data for their further use in developing AI-based forecasts of moisture retention and determining the optimal incorporation depth of bentonite granules.

Field experiments, or trials, are carried out in several stages.

Stage 1: Preparatory stage, March–April.

At the preparatory stage, suitable soil moisture sensors should be selected and installed at soil depths of 10, 15, 20, and 30 cm.

To conduct field trials, information should be collected on the basis of statistical data on precipitation over the last 10 years, and a forecast of precipitation volume during the field trial period should be established. For example, if 150 mm of precipitation is expected in spring, bentonite placed at a depth of 20 cm will maintain moisture above the permanent wilting point until July 15.

Stage 2: Establishment of the experiment, April.

The site allocated for field trials is divided into four randomized blocks, with three replications:

Control (C): traditional sowing without bentonite.

Variation A: uniform application of bentonite at a rate of 20 t/ha into the 0–15 cm soil layer.

Variation B: local band application of granules at a soil depth of 10–30 cm.

Variant C: application of bentonite mixed with additives or fertilizers at the same depth.

Stage 3: Monitoring, May–August.

During this period, the obtained data should be analyzed in real time, including:

– hydration dynamics and assessment of the water absorption rate after spring atmospheric precipitation;

– comparison of the rate of decrease, or reduction, in soil moisture content;

– weekly monitoring of the amount of green biomass, or vegetation.

Stage 4: Evaluation of results, September.

At this stage, the actual soil moisture data should be compared with theoretical calculations based on the Richards equation, followed by adjustment of the model coefficients.

The obtained data should then be entered into the neural network to refine recommendations for the next season.

Required Equipment for Testing

Material: Granulated bentonite from local deposits, for example Navbahor, Azkamar, Vaush, Kattakurgan, Logon, Khovdak, and others.

Technical equipment: A cultivator or motor cultivator equipped with a hopper for deep fertilizer application, preferably modernized for bentonite incorporation.

IT tools: A climate monitoring station and a cloud-based data processing service using Python/TensorFlow.

Scheme for Conducting Experimental Trials

Control: Soil without additives, representing the natural background.

Variant 1: Application of bentonite at a rate of 6 t/ha.

Variant 2: Application of bentonite at a rate of 12 t/ha.

Variant 3: Application of bentonite at a rate of 18 t/ha.

Variant 4: Application of bentonite at a rate of 24–30 t/ha.

Parameters of experimental plots: 25–50 m² for each variant.

- **Incorporation depth:** 0–30 cm, corresponding to the main root-inhabited soil layer.
- **Application method:** Uniform subsurface incorporation into the soil.

Input Data for AI

1. **Soil moisture:** Measurements every 10–15 days and after each rainfall event at depths of 10, 20, 30, and 40 cm.
2. **Meteorological data:** Air temperature, air humidity, precipitation amount and intensity, and solar radiation.
3. **Physical properties:** Bulk density (g/cm³), moisture absorption rate, and field capacity.

2. Data Collection and Processing Methodology

For training a neural network or an algorithm, the data should be structured as time series. It is recommended to combine the thermostat–gravimetric method, which serves as a reference method for calibration, with the installation of soil moisture sensors, such as TDR probes for continuous monitoring [16-18].

For AI-based modeling, a high data frequency is important; for example, sensor readings may be recorded every 15–60 minutes. In this process, sensor errors and measurement noise must be taken into account [19].

It is necessary to establish the relationship between the bentonite application rate and the duration of moisture retention above the plant wilting point. The Van Genuchten model can be used to describe how bentonite changes the soil water potential [20-22].

The developed algorithm should solve the task of predictive management. For example, based on weather forecast data, the AI calculates how much moisture will remain in the bentonite-amended soil layer after one week and signals the need for agrotechnical measures, such as mulching to reduce evaporation [23,24].

The table below presents typical indicators for rainfed lands of Uzbekistan. These data can be used as a baseline for describing your results.

Table. Dynamics of Moisture Retention in the 5–40 cm Soil Layer During the Growing Season

Experimental variant	Bentonite dose, t/ha	Average soil moisture, % of FC*	Average moisture retention period, days	Deviation from AI forecast, %
Control variant, without additives	0	42.0	18	-6.5
VARIANT 1	6	55.8	29	-2.1
VARIANT 2	12	62.4	36	+1.4
VARIANT 3	18	67.8	42	+2.8
VARIANT 4	24–30	70.5	46	+4.1

* FC — field capacity.

Conclusion

The application of modeling methods and artificial intelligence makes it possible to simulate the chemical and mineralogical composition of bentonite granules, as well as the swelling of bentonite due to moisture absorption, the rate of which is controlled by an AI model depending on the average soil temperature. This provides a prolonged moisture-retention effect for 3–5 years.

The integration of AI into the process of bentonite application makes it possible to retain up to 40% of the moisture obtained from spring precipitation in the aeration zone until the end of August. It also contributes to increasing pasture productivity by extending the vegetation period. In addition, the consumption of bentonite can be reduced through targeted application in zones with maximum moisture retention during the growing season under arid climatic conditions. The application of the developed AI algorithms makes it possible to model the soil drying curve with high accuracy. AI successfully identified a nonlinear relationship between the intensity of solar radiation and the rate of moisture release from bentonite hydro-barriers. This allows critical periods of moisture deficit to be predicted several days in advance.

Thus, the use of an intelligent moisture-retention management system makes it possible not only to preserve the ecosystem of rainfed lands, but also to ensure a direct economic effect through two factors: minimizing losses during dry periods and calculating the exact dosage of bentonite, thereby preventing excessive application of costly ameliorants. The use of bentonite clays creates a stable intra-soil hydro-barrier that increases the moisture-retention capacity of rainfed soils. The developed algorithms make it possible to transform random factors, such as precipitation and evaporation, into a controllable model. The combination of natural adsorbents and AI technologies increases the profitability of rainfed agriculture through adaptive resource management under conditions of water scarcity.

The application of AI transforms the use of bentonites from an uncontrolled process into a high-precision land reclamation technology. This represents a strategic direction for ensuring the

rational use of water resources and adapting the agriculture of the Republic of Uzbekistan to climate change.

REFERENCES

1. Ahmed Abdelfattah, H., & Mostafa, H. (2024). Potential of soil conditioners to mitigate deficit irrigation impacts on agricultural crops: A review. *Water Resources Management*, 38(8), 2961–2976. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11269-024-03822-w>
2. Rakhmonov, A. Kh., Tashkuziev, M. M., & Myachina, O. V. (2021). The effect of bentonite-modified fertilizers on the moisture capacity and aggregate composition of soil under cotton. *Universum: Chemistry and Biology*, 7(85). <https://doi.org/10.32743/UniChem.2021.85.7.11932>
3. Zhang, Y., & Liu, X. (2023). Dynamic modeling of soil water release characteristics under extreme temperature fluctuations in amended soils. *Agricultural Water Management*, 288, Article 108473. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.agwat.2023.108473>
4. Singh, D. K., & Rao, S. (2025). Predictive dynamics of soil moisture in arid zones: A nonlinear machine learning approach integrating meteorological and pedological data. *Journal of Arid Environments*, 231. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jaridenv.2024.105436>
5. Vandana, M., et al. (2024). Predicting the hydraulic conductivity of bentonite-amended soils using artificial neural networks. *Scientific Reports*, 14, Article 10738. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41598-024-61434-6>
6. Khaydarov, B. D. (2018). Efficiency of resource-saving soil tillage on rainfed lands of Uzbekistan. *Agrarian Science*, 10, 50–51. <https://doi.org/10.3263/0869-8155-2018-319-10-50-51>
7. Sabirov, B. T., Kadirova, Z. R., Pulatov, Kh. L., Tairov, S. S., & Ergashev, Sh. T. (2021). Research of the basic physical and chemical properties of bentonite clays of promising deposits of Uzbekistan. In *Proceedings of the EURO ASIA 8th International Congress on Applied Sciences* (p. 318). Uzbekistan.
8. Mukhtorova, N. B., Sabirov, B. T., & Aliev, B. A. (2022). Study of the chemical and mineralogical composition of Shafirkan bentonite clay for obtaining new sorbents. *Science and Innovation*, 3, 168–175.
9. Madatov, B. A., Sabirov, B. T., Temirov, U. Sh., & Umkirov, F. E. (2023). Comparative study of physical and technical properties of bentonite clay powders from various deposits. *International Bulletin of Engineering and Technology*, 3(7), 60–66.
10. Muftullaeva, M. B., Reimov, A. M., & Sabirov, B. T. (2023). Chemical composition of bentonite from the Muynak deposit of Karakalpakstan. *Universum: Technical Sciences*, 7(112). <https://doi.org/10.32743/UniTech.2023.112.7.15766>
11. Mukhtorova, N. B., Aliev, B. A., Sabirov, B. T., & Umirov, U. F. (2023). Thermodynamics of the desorption process and features of regeneration of adsorbents based on bentonite clay. *Science and Innovation International Scientific Journal*, 2(9), 81–87. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8367636>
12. Mukhtorova, N. B., Aliev, B. A., Sabirov, B. T., & Umirov, U. F. (2023). Research on the processes of wastewater purification in textile production using bentonite adsorbents. *Science and Innovation International Scientific Journal*, 2(9), 123–129. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8386901>

13. Mukhtorova, N., Aliev, B., Sabirov, B., Umirov, U., Shokhakimova, A., & Ergashev, Y. (2024). Investigation of ion sorption of chromium, zinc, nickel, and cobalt complex compounds from wastewater using bentonite clay. *E3S Web of Conferences*, 497, Article 03046. <https://doi.org/10.1051/e3sconf/202449703046>
14. Sabirov, B. T. (2024). Current state of mining and processing of bentonite clays in Uzbekistan and prospects for their application in the metallurgical industry of the Republic of Belarus. *Casting and Metallurgy*, 3–4, 13–16.
15. Sabirov, B. T. (2025). Current state of mining and processing of bentonite clays in Uzbekistan. *Foundryman of Russia*, 1(16), 23–26.
16. Pulatova, Z. F., Sabirov, B. T., & Pulatov, Kh. L. (2026). Development of a mathematical model of the mechanism of water accumulation, moisture retention, and water release by bentonite clay. *Science and Innovation International Scientific Journal*, 5(3). <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.19363994>
17. Yusupova, N., & Usmonova, M. (2022). Improvement of the reclamation condition of soil resources under the climatic conditions of Uzbekistan. *Innovative Science*, 6-1, 64–66.
18. Mukhamedieva, D. T., Ziyadullaeva, D. Sh., Shamsieva, S. D., Kholikov, M. U., & Asadova, O. S. (2024). Application of artificial intelligence technology in the qualitative assessment of soil fertility based on neural networks. *Science and Innovation: Special Issue “Modern Problems and Prospects of Development of Energy Supply of Digital Technology Facilities”*, 583–591.
19. Tsyppkin, Yu. A., Bliznyukova, T. V., Gavrilyuk, M. N., & Belov, N. S. (2025). Implementation of artificial intelligence in the management system of land and property complexes and land reclamation measures. *International Agricultural Journal*, 8(4), 1129–1143.
20. Yurchenko, I. F. (2022). Land reclamation and hydraulic engineering: Automation of irrigation based on artificial intelligence technologies. *Land Reclamation and Hydraulic Engineering*, 12(4), 233–245.
21. El Monhim, M. H. B., Chenal, J., & Ben Hichou, B. (2024). Artificial intelligence in soil management: The new frontier of smart agriculture. *Water*, 17(9), Article 1351. <https://doi.org/10.3390/w17091351>
22. Al-Taey, D. K., Hussain, A. J., & Kadhum, H. (2023). Bentonite impact on soil properties and biological activity in the face of drought: A review. *IOP Conference Series: Earth and Environmental Science*, 1262, Article 042058. <https://doi.org/10.1088/1755-1315/1262/4/042058>
23. Tefera, M. L., Zeleke, E. B., Pirastru, M., & Melesse, A. M. (2025). Satellite-based machine learning for soil moisture prediction in dryland agricultural systems. *Remote Sensing*, 17(21). <https://doi.org/10.3390/rs17213651>
24. Peng, F., Sun, D., Chen, B., & Gao, Y. (2024). Effective approach to predict the soil-water retention curve of bentonites using nonlinear fitting. *Journal of Hydrology*. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jhydrol.2024.131799>